

Average Adjacency Matrix

(Constructed using working memory data of the 100 subject subset)

Supplementary Figure 1. Average Adjacency Matrix

Subject-wise adjacency matrices were constructed based on working memory task fMRI BOLD time series. These matrices were then averaged across subjects and the average adjacency matrix was plotted with a threshold of $> |.25|$ for the correlation scores.

Reference activation for Working Memory, Language, Fear, and Neutral tasks from the Neurosynth meta-analyses

A. Working memory Glass Brain

B. Language Glass Brain

C. Fear Glass Brain

D. Neutral Glass Brain

Supplementary Figure 2. Reference fMRI Activation

Reference activation maps for the available subtasks were obtained using the meta-analysis association data provided by Neurosynth and visualized on a Glass Brain using the Nilearn and Brainspace packages.